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Love, Indeed

Indeed, the world is so sophisticated,
Yet binded by a cord; we should have witted;
Fondness; affection;
Attachment; devotion;
Sophisticated as love, which indeed a proscription.

By its nature we have said that it clears the blurs,
And then it starts to paint the canvas by spur;
Colors of scarlet and magenta and vermilion,
For its epitome is florid, so dispensable as thou reason.

There's once I felt to be deemed sentient,
Like I'm moved by this person; so indifferent;
Perhaps this insouciance could define my yearning,
The arid and complex, turned piquant and radiant.

In spite of the distance, in existence or in time,
We stood together, as forever be our spine;
The crepuscule of yesterday
Has been drafted in memoir,
For you shaded my life by love,
And then my solace be have sheltered.

The color you pricked filled the grey scheme of me,
Such garden so picturesque, that scent and that rhapsody;
Thine heart by default, yells out of nirvana,
Bestowed by a gift, glittered by such fantasia.

Fantasia, oh yes, by fantasy I seem to live,
For this indulgence of a paramour
Seemed to have its utmost parti pris;
What tied us should never be united

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T'was the promise construed by the heart,
Shalt it be when it's them,
Who first thrived us from the start.

Seeing you by far is a burden down on me,
How hurtful is it more to feel your distance by decree;
This foul state of inferiority, is such a barricade of thorns,
But still by virtue of rectitude, compliance is a sworn.

Now keeping only the remnants of the stolen paradise,
The vignette of our kingdom, there in melancholy it lies;
The fate has been dictated, never would I concur,
For the blame would be eternal, saying,

'It's the love I should have fought for.'

In traverse, as the world sunders the lock and the key,
I'm sauntering over and at the apex I see
The time has its perfection at the moment of its turn,
Indeed, love awaits by chance, for it is the lesson I've learned.